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Article · July 2020

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Workforce diversity and work culture in the IT/ITeS industry, Visakhapatnam

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Received: 22 March 2020 Revised and Accepted: 16 May 2020

ABSTRACT: Workforce diversity is one of the important issues in today's corporate world. Due to globalization, almost all organizations have a variety of employees with different backgrounds, cultures and values, languages, religions, nationalities, skill and knowledge, and generations, etc. Therefore, managing diversity in organizations is crucial in order to harmonize employees of all generations to follow the same organizational culture and motivate them to work in a team for the betterment of the organization. As workplaces are becoming more diverse, employers must be very active to set the plans and policies of the organization in such a way so as to encapsulate the diverse nature of different employees. The organizations must take note of different important factors such as recruitment, communication, and training practices to manage and resolve the differences among the employees if any. In this paper, the researcher tried to know the perceptions of various generations of the workforce on various aspects of the work environment in the IT/ITeS industry. A structured questionnaire was developed and data is collected by survey method with a randomly drawn sample of 575 is taken.

KEY WORDS: workforce diversity, work culture, work environment

I. INTRODUCTION

A population may be divided into distinct segments on the basis of their age or experience. This serves the valuable purpose of identification of work-related preferences and behavioral traits which members belonging to a particular generational cohort exhibit as a result of the major life events which they share. This bifurcation of the workplace leads to a categorization of the individuals into different generations which are different from each other and unique in their own self. The current Indian workforce consists of men and women belonging to different generations, this is specifically true for the knowledge workers as well. The I.T sector also relies heavily on its knowledge workers who come from unique generational leanings and hence it becomes of paramount importance to ensure harmony among the different generations, such that their potential can be fully realized. Not much work has been done regarding generational diversity in the Indian context especially in the IT sector. There exist no major studies on I.T. The scope of the study is thus to find out the specific issues and challenges faced in a multigenerational workforce in the Information Technology sector.

I.T sector faces issues particular to this sector especially when it comes to areas like the use of technology, adaptability to change, etc. However, certain issues like mentoring opportunities and preferred methods of working which hold considerable importance in the corporate sector (and hence in the studies related to that sector) do not affect this sector much. Thus it may be clarified that due to lack of research in this specific sector this study has relied heavily on previous works across different sectors but is also conscious of the subtle and pronounced differences present and hence it needs to be clarified that the results of the study might not be in confirmation of previous findings in other sectors. Also, the aim is to identify those differences and devise ways and means which really work in overcoming these differences. Identifying strategies that work is important so that any detrimental effects of generational assortment can be nipped in the bud. The scope of the study is to understand generational diversity as an essential part of the Indian workforce, where diversity to date primarily refers to only gender, regional and disability studies.

II. 2. LITERATURE REVIEW

A Study on "Managing in a Multi-Generational work Place" conducted by NASSCOM to determine the competencies for the technology and enabled services industry focused to explore competencies needed to manage the Gen-X at work environment. It is because of the financial, economic, and technical shifts that are shaking conventional management styles and work climate. The goal of the above study is to establish an industry-wide perspective through the collection of quantitative and qualitative data through targeting organisations. The above research study was performed on the premise that it is important to investigate both the home environment and the company in order to focus on the competencies required to handle the Gen-Y at the workplace.

Amir Zees a & Ahmed Irma (2012), clarified from their article "Generational Diversity: Strategies to Bridge the Diversity Gap" that the different styles of diversity are important ingredients in the organizational work environment in terms of race ethnicity, gender and age, and these diversities have become a major source of conflict and collaboration. The managers and organizations should promote an open and welcoming environment in which workers can learn about different generations as well as share their thoughts without fear. The increased diversity, however, is assured to deliver incentives for greater creativity and more effective ways of doing business. It is important to note that each generation possesses a diverse set of skills and in different capacities makes a valuable contribution to the workforce.

Namitha Rajani (2012), in her article "Engaging generations at the Workplace" concludes that engaging multiple Generations at the workplace to capitalize on their diverse skills and competencies can be a competitive advantage for them. According to author different generational employees have different values and aspirations but they are making a difference by contributing to the overall development of the organization. The HR practitioners and leaders should work towards understanding the diverse values and aspirations of the employees apart from that the organizations should create the structure that maximizes the collaborations among the different generations and should meet the different needs and aspirations of different generations to build an inclusive and engaged workforce that will ensure the overall business success.

Omkar Sapre(2010), in his article "India Inc. vies for the multi-generation workforce to achieve optimum efficiency," revealed that businesses are collaborating with multi-generation teams with these approaches to promote diversity and actively eradicate bias. The enduring programs that regularly sensitizes employees about organizational priorities allow senior employees the freedom to choose positions using social media networking platforms that holding informal sessions to facilitate collaboration. Employee bonding is taken very seriously for which organizational management is important to make people feel they are needed, resources and motivate them with information.

In a roundtable conference on 'Multigenerational Workforce Diversity,' SHRM India and Prof. VasanthiSrinivasan (2014) presented that generations in Western countries can be identified on the basis in birth-year cohorts, while in the Indian context the generation would be defined on the basis of financial, cultural and demographic factors. Both variables play an important role in assessing specific individuals' beliefs and behaviors, from which they can be categorized into different categories. Generational family-related ideals are likely to build greater spaces in the organizations for cooperation through generations. The study aimed to categorize generations in addition to establishing the structures that will be placed at work by organizations to strengthen multi-generational cooperation and its implications for HRM in the Indian context.

Rodney (2012), explored in her article "Impact of multigenerational diversity in the workplace: A big obstacle to address "where potential organisations need to harness the resources of several generations of their workforce in a manner that contributes to teamwork, deeper information exchange that contributes to innovative approaches and networks that facilitate knowledge sharing and alignment. Among the negative factors that affect the organization are increased creativity, innovation, openness to change, stimulus for creative thinking, cross-pollination of ideas in a constructive way delayed decision-making, ego conflict, confusion and discord. Therefore the collective aim of workers and employers is to control and manage multi-generational workplace diversity.

Based on the above review of the literature on workforce diversity in the workplace, it could be deduced that majority of the studies are focussed on the advantages of generational diversity and there is no much concentration on IT/ITeS industry. Therefore, this research is aimed to fill the gap in the literature, as it focuses on the occurrence of various events where generational differences play a role in the IT/ITeS industry.

III. METHODOLOGY

The data was collected from both primary and secondary sources.

3.1 Sources of Primary and Secondary

The study is based on first hand information as well as secondary data. The key purpose of this research is to examine workplace priorities of different generations on various aspects of human resource activities. The primary data were then obtained from various IT / ITeS workers, Visakhapatnam. A total of 575 questionnaires were

administered among I.T / ITES, Visakhapatnam employees during 2016 in the case of primary data. Secondary data is collected from IT / ITES companies' Articles , Journals, Various websites and annual reports.

3.2 Sampling and Statistical Techniques

This study utilized a technique of convenience sampling to collect primary data. Convenience sampling is a statistical technique of collecting representative data by selecting individuals because of their ease of volunteering or selecting units regardless of their capacity or ease of access. The benefit of such sampling is the simplicity and speed at which data can be collected. The drawbacks are the possibility the sample does not represent the entire population, and volunteers may skew it. Under this report the researcher meets the customers directly according to their convenience and collects data. Therefore, there is a finite number of participants in this sample and their comfort is known.

As per Andhra Pradesh Industrial Infrastructure Corporation (APIIC), there are 13,450 are working in IT / ITES companies, Visakhapatnam. According to the concept of margin of error (4 percent) and 95 percent of confidence level, the required sample is 575. So, the researcher has taken 575 employees as the sample for this study.

3.3 Data Analysis

Data analysis is done using SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Science) version 20.0. The data has been analyzed with the help of required statistical tools such as descriptive statistics, and multiple regression analysis is used to know the impacting factors of workplace according to generational diversity.

IV. DISCUSSION AND FINDINGS

In today's usage, "generation gap" often refers to a perceived gap between younger people and their parents or grandparents. In this context, the researcher attempted to know the factors which impact the work environment due to generational diversity. Multiple regression is used to know the factors which influence the work environment. Perceptions on various factors of the work environment are analyzed based on three generations called elder generation, mid-generation and the younger generation.

It is observed that the elder generation believes that the workers from different generations work effectively together. Also, younger generation respondents perceive that the workers from different generations learn from each other. Almost all generations feel that the Quality of work improves when there are a variety of generational perspectives.

Both elder and younger generations said that the Young generations are keen to learn through mentoring initiatives. And also, the younger generation perceives about creativity as 'Environment conducive, innovation & creativity is created due to the presence of different generations'. The respondents from mid-generation perceived that 'Employees state that coworkers from other generations have a very different perspective about authority & supervision. Younger generations feel that the senior generations look forward to reversing mentoring initiatives.

The p values are less than to 0.05 for the parameters namely 'Workers from different generations learn from each other', 'Inputs from workers of different generations balance one another', 'Environment conducive to innovation & creativity is created due to presence of different generations' which are representing a statistically significant difference between the three generations. There are differences among the three generations on various positive aspects of generational differences.

The p-values of two dimensions namely 'Different generations have conflicts about acceptable work hours', 'Employees complain about the improper mode of communication' are less than to 0.05. These are statistically significant. Therefore, the three generations have different perceptions of 'conflicts' and 'improper mode of communication'.

Regression to know the variables which influence the work environment:

The table below provides a description of the model of multiple regression, which tells the relationship between diversity of the workforce and Independent variables. The researcher has measured the multiple regressions to find out the variables affecting the workplace. The table value R is 0.628, which says there is a positive correlation

between the workforce and various work environment factors. The R² value tells about the percentage of outcome that the predictors describe, i.e., 16 variables.

Table-1: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error
1	.628 ^a	.3893	0.372	0.695
a. Predictors: (Constant), Effective work, learn from each other, Quality of work, mentoring initiatives, inputs from workers, innovation & creativity, new insights, authority & supervision, reverse mentoring, acceptable work hours, do not respect others, communication breakdown, over- or under-reliant on technology, Resentment, improper mode of communication, take co-workers less seriously.				

Dependent Variable: Workforce diversity

Table-2: The significance of the model:

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	14.786	16	.924	1.912	.017 **
Residual	269.638	558	.483		
Total	284.424	574			

** Significance at 0.05

The R² for the model is 0.3893, which means predictors describe 38.93 percent of the overall perception about it. The R² value modified provides an indication of how well the model generalizes the difference (0.3893-0.372) or 1.7%. This shrinkage means that if the model were derived from the population rather than from a sample it would account for about 1.7 percent chance of outcome variation. The F-value 1.912 from the table with p=0.017 is important at the standard significance level of 5 per cent. It can therefore be argued that the multiple regression model results in a substantially improved estimation of the reasons for the interpretation of various variables towards the work environment.

The table below provides the details of the parameters of the model (beta values) and meaning of those values. From the table, b₀ is 1.444 and this can be interpreted as the model predicts that the perception will be 1.444 when there are no predictors (when X =). The value of b₁=0.033 implies that an increase in 1 unit perception of the product results in an increase in overall perception in the workplace by 0.033 times. Similarly, the remaining variables are values b.

Table-3: Showing un-standardized and standardized coefficient values for an understanding of perception towards work environment

Parameters	Un-standardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.444	.189		7.652	.000
Effective work	.033	.048	.033	.684	.004 **
learn from each other	.021	.050	.022	.418	.000 *
Quality of work	.082	.050	.078	1.643	.001*
mentoring initiatives	.015	.048	.016	.317	.000 *
inputs from workers	.063	.048	.064	1.309	.191
innovation & creativity	.042	.049	.044	.854	.03**
new insights	.001	.043	.001	.025	.980
authority & supervision	.042	.047	.049	.893	.000 *
reverse mentoring	.041	.053	.043	.771	.001 *
acceptable work hours	.025	.049	.026	.512	.609
do not respect others	-.029	.048	-.028	-.615	.539
communication breakdown	.025	.046	.026	.545	.021**
over- or under-reliant on technology	-.005	.040	-.006	-.123	.000 *
Resentment	-.005	.046	-.006	-.108	.914
improper mode of communication	.016	.051	.016	.317	.751
take co-workers less seriously	-.012	.046	-.011	-.249	.803

a. Dependent Variable: Generation; *Significance at 0.01; ** Significance at 0.05.

It is interpreted that, the p-values of the parameters are less than to 0.05. so, the work environment is impacted by the variables ‘Effective work’, ‘learn from each other’, ‘Quality of work’, ‘mentoring initiatives’, ‘innovation & creativity’, ‘authority & supervision’, ‘reverse mentoring’, ‘communication breakdown’, ‘over- or under-reliant on technology’.

V. CONCLUSION

In this digital era, generation is often play an important role in the workplace. Different generations may take decisions differently in uncertain situations. So, the researcher tried to know the perceptions of different generation’s employees. The study is carried with a sample of 575. the elder generation believes that the workers from different generations work effectively together. Also, younger generation respondents perceive that the workers from different generations learn from each other. Almost all generations feel that the Quality of work improves when there are a variety of generational perspectives. Both elder and younger generations said that the Young generations are keen to learn through mentoring initiatives. And also, the younger generation perceives about creativity as ‘Environment conducive, innovation & creativity is created due to the presence of different generations’. The respondents from mid-generation perceived that ‘Employees state that coworkers from other

generations have a very different perspective about authority & supervision. Younger generations feel that the senior generations look forward to reversing mentoring initiatives.

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